

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSES OF MULTIPLE DELAMINATIONS IN CURVED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Keywords: *delamination, cohesive elements, explicit code, fibre bridging*

1 Introduction

Delamination represents one of the most important damage phenomena that can affect and limit the application field of a composite structural component. Several studies confirm that the nucleation and subsequent propagation of a single delamination, in a generic composite laminate, can be efficiently simulated by finite elements approaches based on cohesive zone model [1]. However, application of conventional approaches based on cohesive elements presents some limits to model the onset of multiple delaminations, which require the development of numerical models with several cohesive layers until the limit of a cohesive layer for each interface between adjacent plies is reached. In particular, in the case of curved laminates, delaminations represent a fundamental failure mode, which can be activated in quasi-static load conditions and multiple delaminations are often developed. Moreover, delaminations can evolve with different regimes of propagation and different effects on the load carrying capability of the damaged composite structure [2, 3]. Indeed, the distinction between cracks that propagate in stable or unstable regimes is fundamental to understand how delamination can affect the response of a composite structure. Explicit integration schemes could represent an effective solution to reliably predict the propagation mode of delamination in numerical analyses because quasi-static explicit analyses can model progressive crack propagation as well as the dynamic processes that occur in unstable conditions. Unfortunately, application of cohesive elements in quasi-static analyses of multiple delaminations carried out by using explicit FE codes pose considerable numerical difficulties. Such difficulties

can be related to the fact that traditional cohesive approaches are based on elements with zero or infinitesimal thickness and require high penalty stiffness values to avoid relative motion before the fracture onset [4]. The value of penalty stiffness should be inversely proportional to the thickness of the connected sub-laminate [4], so that penalty stiffness increases with the number of cohesive layers represented in the FE scheme. It is well known that high penalty stiffness values can negatively affect both the response [5-7] and the computational time cost of a FE model solved by means of an explicit approach, so that quasi-static analyses including a large number of cohesive layers become very difficult to be performed.

Moving from such considerations, the paper presents a modelling technique particularly suited to analyses carried out by means of explicit time integration schemes. The technique does not require the introduction of penalty stiffness and significantly reduces the numerical problems of traditional cohesive element approaches. Such modelling approach is presented in the first section of the paper and subsequently applied to perform explicit analyses of composite laminates made of a unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy system (CYTEC S2/5216) in different conditions. Experiments and analyses referred to pre-damaged specimens undergoing stable and unstable interlaminar crack propagation in mode I and mode II standard test configurations are presented. The approach adopted to model the effect of fibre bridging phenomenon during delamination is also presented. Finally the approach is applied to model the response of an originally undamaged curved composite laminate subjected to a tensile load condition. Such application will show the capability of the proposed

cohesive approach to simulate the onset and subsequent propagation of multiple interlaminar cracks, with different propagation regimes, by means of qualitative and quantitative correlation with experimental evidences.

2 Proposed cohesive modelling approach

If a traditional cohesive zone modelling approach is adopted in an analysis conducted by using an explicit time integration scheme, the stiffness of the cohesive elements will directly affect the stable time step leading to very high computational costs [8]. In order to overcome such difficulty, an alternative modelling technique is proposed, based on the different roles that are actually played by the in-plane and the out-of-plane stress components acting in a laminate [9].

Fig. 1. Stress resultants acting on a single lamina in bending conditions (A) and proposed finite element scheme (B).

The consideration at the basis of the modelling strategy can be pointed out considering a laminate in a very simple bending condition, as in Fig. 1.(A). The translational equilibrium of a sub-lamina or of a single lamina can be formalised as in Eq. (1), considering the membrane force per unit width, \$N\$, and the shear stress transferred through the interfaces.

$$\frac{dN_{xx}}{dx} = \tau_{xz}(z+dz) - \tau_{xz}(z) \quad (1)$$

Hence, the area of the lamina cross-section could be lumped at the lamina mid-plane and represented by a bi-dimensional element, such as a membrane or a shell element. Equilibrium can be achieved by connecting such bi-dimensional elements with the use of elements only carrying the out-of-plane stress components. Conventional brick elements with a constitutive behaviour characterised by a null in-plane response could be adopted as connecting elements. Fig. 1.(B) presents the resulting finite element scheme. In order to introduce a cohesive zone model into the interface elements, the fracture process in mode I, II and III are described by the relative displacements at the mid-planes of such sub-laminates, Fig. 2.(A). The components of the relative displacement vector (\$\Delta = U^+ - U^-\$) can be associated to the three possible fracture modes, as indicated in Eq. (2).

$$\Delta_I = \begin{cases} \Delta_z & \text{if } \Delta_z > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \Delta_z \leq 0 \end{cases}; \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta_{II} = \Delta_x; \quad \Delta_{III} = \Delta_y$$

Moreover, within a small strain assumption, \$\Delta\$, can be related to the average strain state in the solid element, \$\epsilon\$. If the vector of displacement discontinuities \$\delta\$ is conceptually replaced by \$\Delta\$, Eq. (3) can be used to convert a generic traction-displacement law into a stress-strain law to be attributed to the solid element, which will transmit only out-of-plane stress components. In the elastic range, such law will be calibrated by the out-of-plane stiffness of the composite material, without requiring any penalty stiffness.

$$\epsilon = \left\{ \epsilon_{zz} \quad \gamma_{xz} \quad \gamma_{yz} \right\}^T = \Delta / t_k \quad (3)$$

A scalar damage variable is then introduced to represent the stiffness properties degradation during the evolution of the fracture process, according to the bi-linear \$\sigma\$-\$\epsilon\$ response, presented in Fig. 2.(B). Hence, the constitutive response attributed to the solid element will follow Eq. (4).

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_{zz} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & G_{xz} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{yz} \end{bmatrix} (1-d) \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{zz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The numerical evaluations presented in [9] indicate that the modelling technique is adequate to represent the quasi-static or dynamic bending behaviour of laminates in the elastic range.

Fig. 2. Description of the interlaminar fracture process (A) and bi-linear constitutive law (B) in the proposed modelling approach.

The onset and the evolution of the damage variable introduced in Eq. (4) can be set to model the strength and the toughness of the interlaminar layers. To accomplish such objective, the proposed approach exploits the links between the critical energy release rates and the energy dissipated in the damage process within the interface element [10, 11]. Taking into consideration Eq. (3), the link between the strain-stress response and the energy release rates for fracture modes I and II can be expressed as in Eq. (5).

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\infty} \sigma_{zz} d\Delta_I &= t_k \int_0^{\infty} \sigma_{zz} d\varepsilon_{zz} = G_{Ic} \\ \int_0^{\infty} \tau_{xz} d\Delta_{II} &= t_k \int_0^{\infty} \tau_{xz} d\gamma_{zx} = G_{IIc} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Equations (4) and (5) allow modelling the strength and the toughness of the cohesive interface by attributing a bi-linear stress vs. strain response to the solid element, as the one presented in Fig. 2.(B).

In the constitutive model, properties in mode II and mode III are considered identical. Damage onset in processes evolving in pure mode I or mode II occurs beyond the peak stress σ_{I0} and σ_{II0} , which represent the normal and shear strength of the interlaminar layer. Mixed mode processes are addressed by introducing the mixed-mode criterion proposed by Benzeggagh and Kenane [12] (*B-K criterion*). The criterion is based on the expression reported in Eq. (6), where η represents an experimental parameter that was set equal to 1.45 [10, 11].

$$G_c = G_{Ic} + (G_{IIc} - G_{Ic}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right)^\eta \quad (6)$$

with: $G_T = (G_I + G_{II})$

The resulting cohesive law was implemented in a *Fortran Vumat* subroutine to be linked to the *3DS/Abaqus Explicit Code* [8].

Globally, it should be observed that the proposed approach does not introduce free surfaces that do not exist at the beginning of the computation and does not require the traditional cohesive elements with infinitesimal or zero thickness. As a consequence, all the material characteristics can be directly determined on the basis of physical considerations without introducing non-physical penalty stiffness, which can severely affect computational costs and the numerical performances. Therefore, the approach can be conveniently applied in explicit analyses to model laminates with several interfaces, all of them representing a potential location of damage onset, without posing convergence problems and with limited computational costs with respect to traditional approaches.

3. Fracture propagation in pre-damaged specimens

This section presents the test campaign performed to characterise the interlaminar toughness properties of the unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy system (CYTEC S2/5216) considered in this work. In particular, four experimental tests were performed with Double

Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens and four with four-point bend End Notched Flexure (4ENF) configuration to identify interlaminar toughness in mode I and II, respectively. Specimens with a length of 300 mm, a width of 25 mm, and a $[0]_{48}$ lay-up sequence were used. A pre-induced interlaminar crack was produced by means of the interposition of a 13 μm -thick film of Teflon[®] PTFE sheet, with a length of 80 mm, at the mid-plane of each laminate. The final mean cured thickness of all the specimens was about of 10.39 mm.

Fig. 3. Fibre bridging phenomenon during crack propagation.

DCB tests were performed as prescribed by ASTM D5528 [13], by adopting an MTS 858 with a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min during loading and 5 mm/min during unloading. Crack advancement was monitored by means of a dedicated picture acquisition system. Fibre bridging phenomenon was observed during the opening phase at the crack tip, as confirmed by Fig. 3. The resistance curves (*R-curves*), reported in Fig. 4, were defined for the DCB specimens tested by applying each of the four data reduction methods proposed by ASTM D5528 [13].

Fig. 4. Experimental *R-curves* obtained with four different data reduction methods for DCB specimens.

All methods confirm the presence of a significant *R-curve* effect. In fact, fracture toughness (G_R) increase with crack length (Δa), from an initial (G_{Ri}) value of about 0.2 kJ/m^2 up to a steady state toughness (G_{Rss}) value of about 0.8 kJ/m^2 . Such behaviour can be explained by the development of a fracture process zone (*FPZ*) during the crack process. In this case the length required by the crack to reach a steady propagation, known as characteristic length (l_{FPZ}), can be considered of about 100–110 mm.

Fig. 5. Configuration of ENF (A) and 4ENF (B) tests.

To investigate the response during the stable propagation of delamination in Mode II, a series of four-point bend End Notched Flexure (4ENF) tests were performed on four different specimens with the same geometry of the ones tested in Mode I. The typical stable propagation regime offered by 4ENF test made possible the monitoring of the interlaminar crack during its growth in Mode II and consequently to identify several toughness values in correspondence of the crack advancement. The pre-opening phase was promoted in unstable regime by means of a conventional three-point bend End Notched Flexure (ENF) tests with $a = 37.5$ mm and $L = 62.5$ mm (Fig. 5.(A)). After this phase each of the four pre-opened specimens, was tested in a four-point bending configuration, with the set-up reported in Fig. 5.(B) with $a = 43.75$ mm, $2L = 125$ mm and $L_i = 75$ mm. Tests were carried out in control displacement condition by adopting an MTS 858 system with a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min.

As proposed in [14] the compliance calibration technique (CC) was adopted to determinate toughness from 4ENF test data, in agreement with:

$$G_c = \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad (7)$$

The application of Eq. (7) require to determine the critical load at which growth occurs (P_c), the width of the specimen (B), compliance (C) and in particular the slope of the compliance vs. crack length curve ($\partial C / \partial a$). In order to define such derivative four 4ENF tests have been performed after the pre-opening test, considering five different positions of the crack tip ($a^i = 25; 30; 35; 40; 45$ mm) at a moderate load level well below the value required to promote the propagation of the crack.

The same procedure described in [14] was adopted to generate the compliance (C) against crack length (a) curve. The monitoring of crack propagation during the test, by means of the same camera system adopted in DCB tests, has permitted to correlate the maximum load level (P_{max}) supported by the specimen with the crack length (a) and consequently, thanks to Eq. (7) to define *R-curves* reported in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Experimental R-curves obtained with Compliance Calibration method for 4ENF tests.

The trend of mode II toughness values (G_{IIIR}) against crack length (a), in agreement with the increase of the load level supported by the specimens during crack propagation, indicates the presence of a quite significant *R-curves* effect. This effect led the fracture toughness in Mode II from a mean value of

about 1.8 kJ/m² up to a mean value of about 2.2 kJ/m². Further experimental investigations on the actual effects of this phenomenon are required as well as the correlation with the numerical model to evaluate, for instance, the frictional influence on this behaviour, as reported in [15].

3.1 Modeling Mode I fracture propagation in the presence of fiber bridging effect

Recent studies [16-19] confirm the possibility to model an *R-curve* response and a long process zone by superposing two different bilinear cohesive laws, with its own characteristic length l_{c1} and l_{c2} . The resulting response is a trilinear constitutive law, as reported in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Trilinear cohesive law obtained by superimposing two bilinear laws.

The parameters of each bilinear cohesive law were determined on the basis of the experimental DCB *R-curves* shown in Fig. 4, adopting the procedure presented in [18]. In fact, there are only two unknown parameters n and m that permit to completely define cohesive strengths as well as fracture toughnesses for both the bilinear cohesive laws, in agreement with the relations reported in Fig. 7, with $n \geq 0$ and $m \leq 1$. In particular, from the DCB *R-curves* (Fig. 4) it can be observed that the onset of crack propagation is characterised by an initial toughness value of about 0.2 kJ/m², whereas after a propagation length approximately of 100 mm a steady state toughness value of about 0.8 kJ/m² is reached. These values allowed directly defining $G_1 = 0.2$ kJ/m², $G_c = 0.8$ kJ/m² and the parameter m as $m = G_1 / G_c = 0.25$. Finally, the solution of a semi-analytical expression proposed in [18] that accounts for the effects of adherend thickness and the combined effects of two superposed bilinear

cohesive laws has permitted to define the strength ratio parameter: $n = 0.9917$.

In the present work, both conventional and proposed cohesive zone approach were applied with the superposition of the two bilinear cohesive laws. Therefore, two different models representing a DCB specimen with an initial crack length of 45 mm respect to the points of loading application were developed. In agreement with the results exposed in [18] only a strip of 1/10 of the width of the specimens tested was considered for both the models. A typical element size of 0.5 mm was adopted along the direction of crack propagation.

The conventional cohesive zone model was developed to be solved by an implicit code (*ABAQUS Standard* [8]). Each DCB arm was modelled by using two incompatible-mode elements (*C3D8I* [8]) through the thickness, as shown in Fig. 8.(A). The only one interlaminar layer in this model consists of two superposed traditional 8-node cohesive elements (*COH3D8* [8]) with $\sigma_c = \sigma_{t0} = 20$ MPa, $G_c = 0.8$ kJ/m², $m = 0.25$ and $n = 0.9917$.

Fig. 8. DCB test: conventional cohesive model for implicit code (A), and proposed cohesive model for explicit code (B).

A model refined at the level of the single ply was developed with the proposed hybrid scheme, and solved by an explicit integration approach (*ABAQUS Explicit* [8]). This hybrid FE scheme is composed by 48 shell elements (*S4R* [8]) layers disposed in the mid-plane of each of the 48 plies of the DCB specimen and consequently by 47 solid elements

(*C3D8R* [8]) layers disposed at the interface between two adjacent plies, as shown in Fig. 8.(B).

Shell elements, that represent the in-plane behaviour of each lamina, were characterised by a purely elastic orthotropic material model with the in-plane elastic properties reported in Tab. 1. Solid elements, that model the out-of-plane response of each lamina, were endowed with the bilinear stress-strain constitutive law described in section 2 and characterised by the physical out-of-plane elastic moduli of the material, also reported in Tab. 1.

Tab. 1. Elastic properties of glass fibre/epoxy system (CYTEC S2/5216).

E_{11}	(GPa)	47.5
$E_{22} = E_{33}$	(GPa)	13.5
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$		0.257
ν_{23}		0.3
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	(GPa)	5.896
G_{23}	(GPa)	5.192

The interlaminar layer at the mid plane of the DCB specimen was completed by the superposition of another layer of interface solid elements (*C3D8R* [8]) with the same properties previously defined for the conventional cohesive model. The link between mid-plane relative displacement and strains in the connecting elements was opportunely modified in order to take into account large displacements. The explicit FE analyses were performed by means of a velocity boundary condition applied to the loading tip with an appropriate time history to avoid onset of dynamic oscillation during the loading phase.

Qualitative and quantitative comparisons between the two different approaches, in terms of interlaminar damage evolution and load vs. displacement response are presented in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively. The load-displacement response of the proposed cohesive approach is very close the numerical response of traditional cohesive approach and both are in good agreement with the experimental curves, in particular, for displacement larger than 15 mm, as shown in Fig. 9. Such result confirms the correct estimation of the steady state toughness value $G_c = 0.8$ kJ/m². Discrepancy between numerical and experimental responses is appreciable at the onset of crack propagation, probably indicating a slight overestimation of the

initial fracture toughness ($G_i = G_l = 0.2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$). The optimization process reported in [18] could be adopted to improve the identification of the trilinear law.

Fig. 9. Numerical-experimental correlation of the load vs. displacement response in DCB tests.

3.2 Modeling of stable and unstable Mode II fracture propagation

The proposed cohesive approach was also adopted to develop models of ENF and 4ENF tests. The knowledge of the position of the interlaminar layer undergoing delamination allows limiting the adoption of the proposed cohesive approach only for the interlaminar layers close to the mid plane of the ENF specimens. Accordingly, only 4 sub-laminates, at the level of the single ply, were modeled by means of shell elements (*S4R* [8]) layers disposed in the mid-plane of each ply, mutually connected through the thickness by solid elements (*C3D8R* [8]). Continuum shell elements were introduced in the model to represent the remaining part of the two arms of the specimen. All the interface elements were characterised by the out-of plane elastic properties reported in Tab. 1 and by an interlaminar shear strength of $\sigma_{IIO} = 50 \text{ MPa}$. All the width of the specimens was considered in the model. The pre-opening interface was modeled by defining an initial damage condition to the cohesive elements of the mid-plane interface, respecting the initial crack length “*a*” of the specimens tested. The same mesh scheme was used to model both ENF and 4ENF tests, as reported in Fig. 10.(A) and Fig. 10.(B)

respectively. In the first case, three rigid cylindrical surfaces were analytically defined in order to model both the upper load application roller and the two lower ones. In the 4ENF model the load was introduced by the definition of a rigid surface including both load-application rollers. Rotation of such rigid body was left unconstrained as in the real fixture, as presented in Fig. 10.(B).

Fig. 10. Final interlaminar damage configuration of the proposed cohesive model of ENF (A) and 4ENF (B) tests.

A penalty contact algorithm was defined both in the ENF and 4ENF model to create the interaction between all the rigid analytical surfaces and the external surfaces of the specimens. The upper rigid bodies were moved downward by using an appropriate velocity law in order to avoid high frequency mode excitation.

Quantitative numerical-experimental correlation in terms of load vs. displacement trends for both the ENF test configurations is reported in Fig. 11. The proposed models correctly capture the linear response of ENF and 4ENF tests until crack propagation and subsequently correctly predict the unstable and the stable propagation of interlaminar fracture in mode II.

A sensitivity study on mode II fracture toughness was performed on the basis of the resistance shown in Fig. 6. In particular, three different values were considered: 1.8; 2.0; 2.2 kJ/m^2 . The first value of $G_{IIC} = 1.8 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ provides a good correlation with the load history during 4ENF experiments. It can also be observed that the final part of the response is captured, including the change of slope when the crack passes below the second load application roller. Such results indicate that the response of 4

ENF test can be modelled by using a constant value of interlaminar toughness, although the data reduction scheme suggests a progressive increment of G_{IIc} with the crack length.

Fig. 11. Numerical-experimental comparison of load vs. displacement response in 4ENF and in ENF test.

The best correlation with the response of ENF test is obtained by using a G_{IIc} of 2.0 kJ/m^2 . The discrepancy between the value considered in the 4ENF test ($G_{IIc} = 1.8 \text{ kJ/m}^2$) and the one considered in the ENF test ($G_{IIc} = 2.0 \text{ kJ/m}^2$) is compatible with the scattering of the toughness values identified by 4ENF tests, as confirmed by the sensitivity study, in terms of load-displacement response, reported in Fig. 12.

Frictional effects between the arms of the 4 ENF specimens were also taken in to account. The numerical trends reported in Fig. 12 are related to three different models characterised by the same fracture toughness value of $G_{IIc} = 1.8 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ and three friction coefficients: $\mu = 0.1$; 0.3 ; 0.5 . The increase of the friction coefficients tends not only to increase the load level at the initiation of crack propagation but also to increase the resistance of the specimen with respect to crack propagation. This aspect, that was observed in [15] only for Over Notched Flexure (ONF) test and not for 4ENF test is probably due, in this case, both to the characteristics of the system material considered and to the experimental set-up selected.

Fig. 12. Fracture toughness sensitivity and frictional effects on the numerical-experimental comparison of load vs. displacement response in 4ENF. For clarity, the comparison of frictional effects curves was offset by 1.5 mm.

4. Tensile load tests on curved composite laminates without pre-damage

Two curved beam specimens made of unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy system (CYTEC S2/5216), previously characterised by means of DCB and ENF tests, were manufactured with a homogeneous stacking sequence of 48 plies $[0]_{48}$, in agreement with the geometrical lay-out proposed by the ASTM standard [20].

Fig. 13. Strain gauges disposition on the curved beam (CB) specimen (A) and lay-out of the tensile load test performed on MTS system (B).

Both specimens were instrumented with four strain-gauges disposed in a back-to-back configuration as reported in Fig. 13.(A). The tests were performed by means of an MTS/810 testing machine, clamping the tips of each specimen through a couple of grips, specifically designed to leave completely free the

rotational degree of freedom of the specimen around a transversal axis. Fig. 13.(B) shows a detail of the test lay-out with the specimen connected to the MTS testing machine. In order to perform a quasi-static load condition, each specimen was tested at a cross head speed of 1 mm/min. Both the specimens tested have shown a similar behaviour with the nucleation and subsequent propagation of three different interlaminar failure events as clearly presented by the sequence of Fig. 14.(A).(B).(C), and of Fig. 14.(D).(E).(F) for specimen *CB#1* and *CB#2* respectively.

Fig. 14. Interlaminar crack evolution observed for *CB#1* test (A)-(B)-(C) and *CB#2* test (D)-(E)-(F).

The development of these crack propagation events has followed a different sequence in the two specimens. Indeed, the first interlaminar damage occurred approximately at one third of the thickness of the specimen in both the tests, but the second crack originated at different locations: between the position of the first delamination and the inner radius in the *CB#1* test, as shown in Fig. 14.(B), and between the first delamination and the external radius in the *CB#2* test, as shown in Fig. 14.(E). The opposite occurred in the third failure event: a new delamination developed above the first one in the *CB#1* specimen (Fig. 14 (C)) and below the first one, in an interface very close to the inner radius, in the *CB#2* specimen (Fig. 14 (F)). Load vs. displacement response for both the specimens as well as strain gauges responses were recorded during the tests. Figure 15 shows the load vs. displacement trends for the two specimens tested.

Fig. 15. Load vs. displacement response of the two specimens tested *CB#1* and *CB#2*.

After an initial small adjustment phase, both specimens have shown a linear response until a limit load level in correspondence of the nucleation of the first delamination, which occurred at about 0.9 kN and 0.7 kN for specimen *CB#1* and *CB#2* respectively. A sudden load drop occurs after the maximum load level was reached. Both specimens did not completely lose their load carrying capability because the propagation of delamination was arrested after the unstable phase. In this new damaged configuration both specimens are able to sustain a certain amount of load until a new level of force required to create a new interlaminar damage is reached. This is confirmed by the reduction of the stiffness of the laminate after each sudden load drop.

Fig. 16. FE model of the curved beam specimen.

A FE model of the curved beam test was developed on the basis of the proposed numerical technique. All interlaminar layers were modelled in the central part of the curved laminate. As a consequence, a scheme with 48 sub-laminates, modelled by means

of shell elements (*S4R* [8]), connected by 47 layers of solid elements (*C3D8R* [8]) was adopted. The lateral arms of the specimen were modelled by adopting a continuum shell FE scheme (elements *SC8R* [8]). The two dissimilar meshes were joined by a tie connection algorithm [8]. The in-plane mesh grid dimension is approximately of 1.0 mm x 1.0 mm, in the inner part of the curved area of the specimen. Solid elements were characterised by the physical out-of-plane moduli reported in Tab. 1 and by the toughness values identified in the characterization tests. In particular, the initial critical fracture toughness in mode I, $G_{Ic} = 0.2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ and the lowest value in mode II $G_{IIc} = 1.8 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ were considered. Shell and continuum shell elements were characterised by a purely elastic orthotropic material model with the elastic properties reported in Tab. 1. Boundary conditions were introduced in the models by defining two reference nodes in the position of the hinges in the test configuration, and by connecting these two reference nodes to the tip of the model with two rigid bodies. According to this approach, one of the two reference nodes was clamped, except for the rotational DOF around the transversal axis of the specimen. At the other reference node, an appropriate velocity law in the longitudinal direction was defined, in order to reproduce the opening action, in a quasi-static regime, applied to each specimen by the MTS testing machine. All DOFs of this reference node were clamped; with the exception of the rotational one. All the quasi static analyses were performed by means of *Abaqus Explicit* code [8].

The qualitative response of the numerical model appears in acceptable agreement with the experiments. The numerical response can be considered a combination of the two damage modes observed in test considering the localization of the delamination and the sequence of crack events. In fact, the numerical approach captures the position of the first delamination with a good accuracy, as shown in Fig. 17.(A), but predicts the contemporaneous development of the other two cracks, as indicated in Fig. 17.(B). The comparison between the numerical and experimental damage scenarios confirms the capability of the proposed cohesive approach to identify the different locations of interlaminar damage onset, as well as to follow their unstable propagation in the absence of a pre-damaged area.

Fig. 17. First (A) and final (B) interlaminar damage configuration in the proposed cohesive model of curved beam specimen.

Figure 18 shows the numerical-experimental correlation in terms of load vs. displacement response for a specific set of interlaminar strength values ($\sigma_{I0} = 35 \text{ MPa}$ and $\sigma_{II0} = 70 \text{ MPa}$). ILSS tests were performed to identify the shear strength value, whereas the peeling strength was set by means of a sensitivity study. In fact, in agreement with the indication of the ASTM Standard [20], the response was found very sensitive to this last interlaminar strength value (σ_{I0}). As a matter of fact, such a strength value affects the maximum peak load reached by the specimen before the first significant load drop, in correspondence of unstable propagation of the first interlaminar damage, qualitatively reported in Fig. 17.(A). The numerical model correctly represents the linear response of the two curved specimens until a maximum load level of about 0.70 kN in agreement with the value measured for the *CB#2* specimen. As previously observed, for the qualitative response of the model, the contemporary development of the second and third delamination leads the numerical load vs. displacement response to be characterised by the presence of only two significant load drops. For such reason the response of the model is not able to accurately represent the post failure behaviour of the specimen between the second and third event. However, it should be observed that the stiffness of the specimen after the load drops is in good

agreement with the experimental response after the delamination events.

Fig. 18. Numerical-experimental comparison of load vs. displacement response for curved beam tests.

Sensitivity study on the fracture toughness in mode I and mode II showed a little appreciable effect of the value in mode I particularly for the maximum peak load reached by the numerical model and no significant effect of the value in mode II. Finally, the results of a model performed by the superposition of two cohesive elements with a bilinear response in all the 47 interlaminar layers of the hybrid scheme, confirmed the negligible influence of the fibre bridging phenomenon on the response of curved beam specimens. Such result is in agreement with the small level of opening in mode I experienced by all the interlaminar cracks originated in the specimens. Further improvements of the model require an extension of the detailed hybrid scheme along the lateral arms, and also a probabilistic distribution of the strength properties.

5. Conclusions

The paper presents an alternative cohesive modelling approach particularly suitable to manage models of composite laminates characterised by the presence of several interlaminar layers. The technique adapts a cohesive model presented in literature to the description of a composite laminate as a collection of bi-dimensional elements representing sub-laminates, which are mutually connected by interface elements. Such elements are

characterised by a null in-plane response and by a non-linear out-of-plane behaviour, which models the onset and propagation of interlaminar damage. This hybrid FE scheme avoids the need to introduce non-physical penalty stiffness, as in traditional cohesive element approaches allowing an efficient solution by means of an explicit integration scheme without an excessive reduction of stable integration time steps. Hence, explicit analyses can be performed at a reasonable computational cost in order to efficiently model both static and dynamic problems.

The approach has been initially applied to model DCB and ENF tests both in three-point and four-point bending configurations. The numerical-experimental correlations showed the capability of the numerical approach to reproduce well the load-displacement response recorded in DCB tests during the stable propagation of interlaminar crack in mode I, in the presence of a considerable fibre-bridging effect. In fact, the versatility of the proposed approach has permitted to easily perform analyses with the superposition of two bi-linear cohesive responses following a semi-analytical procedure based on the experimental DCB *R-curves*. Similar good results in terms of load-displacement numerical vs. experimental correlations were obtained in the simulation of mode II interlaminar crack propagation both in unstable and stable regime of propagation observed in ENF and 4ENF tests, respectively. Sensitivity analyses on the effects of mode II fracture toughness values and of friction coefficients on the numerical response of 4ENF tests were performed. In particular, the latter ones confirmed the significant role played by the frictional contact between crack faces under the loading points during crack propagation on the load-displacements response of 4ENF tests.

The numerical technique has been subsequently applied to model the interlaminar fracture onset and propagation within an undamaged curved laminate in a quasi-static tensile load condition. The comparison between the numerical and experimental damage patterns points out both the capability of the technique to identify the different locations of the interlaminar damage onset in the absence of pre-damage zones in the laminates and its capability to follow the propagation of multiple interlaminar cracks. The numerical-experimental correlation of load vs. displacement curves shows that the numerical approach can capture all the most

significant quantitative aspects of the experimental response in terms of stiffness, maximum load peak before the onset of damage, and load levels during the stable propagation of multiple delaminations.

Acknowledgements

The sponsorship of project “*STIMA – Strutture Ibride per Meccanica ed Aerospazio*” co-founded by Regione Lombardia is gratefully acknowledged.

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